

Humanitarian Support of India to Sri Lankan Economic Crisis : A Study During Post-Covid period

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ABSTRACT

India and Sri Lanka share historical, economic, intellectual, cultural, religious, and ethnic intimacy, and their relationship stretches back to nearly 2500 years. Their friendship and cooperation shone through in the post-COVID-19 Sri Lankan economic debacle. India stood by her South Asian neighbour like a rock of Gibraltar, extending all possible help and support to ensure normalcy in the Island nation at the earliest.

KEY WORDS : Covid-19, Easter Sunday, IMF, Economic Crisis, Organic Farming, COVID-19, Sri Lanka, Sri Lankan Central Bank)

INTRODUCTION

Before proceeding into India's humanitarian support to Sri Lanka during the post-COVID economic crisis, it would be relevant to shed ample light upon the prominent factors resulting in the Island nation's plunge into this unprecedented crisis. Of the many factors contributing to the current economic crisis in Lanka from 2019, the most prominent one has been economic mishandling by the successive government, an alarming rise in foreign debt, diminishing foreign reserves, as well as devaluation of Sri Lankan currency and skyrocketing prices. To make matters worse, there was substantial tax reduction, money creation and a national policy shift towards organic and biological farming. Furthermore, incidents like the Easter bomb attacks and the COVID-19 virus are heightening the crisis. All these factors snowball into a precarious economic condition that Sri Lanka faced.

At this critical juncture, when the Sri Lankan economy was in tatters, India stepped in with timely humanitarian support to bring the once vibrant economy back to normalcy. India is highly committed to extending all sorts of assistance to the neighbouring countries under

its Neighbourhood First Policy. As Sri Lanka has been going through its worst possible economic crisis since its independence, India has extended all possible help and support to bring the struggling nation's shambolic economy back on track.

Factors Responsible for Sri Lanka's Economic Crisis

The economic meltdown of Sri Lanka was not an overnight phenomenon, and a cluster of factors can be

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attributed to the Lankan economy's debacle. Here, an attempt has been made to discuss these factors briefly in the first section before proceeding to India's timely support to help the Island nation resurrect the flailing economy.

- **The Easter Bombing and its Effect on Tourism** – The 2019 Easter bombing can rightly be summed up as the precursor to the economic crisis as it set into motion a series of bomb blasts in churches and luxury hotels where more than 250 casualties were recorded, leading to approximately 71% decline in international tourist arrival thereby crippling the sunshine industry and rendering a sizeable population dependent upon it unemployed. The recession in tourism put enormous strains on Sri Lanka's foreign exchange reserves in 2019. (Ramkumar, 2022:14)
- **COVID-19 Pandemic in Sri Lanka and its Effect on the Economy** – The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic after these economic pitfalls made the nation's financial health awful. The export of items like tea, coffee, rubber, spices, minerals and garments suffered. With the fall in tourism, remittance defaulted as job cuts became the norm. COVID-19 necessitates government expenditure. While the fiscal deficit exceeded 10% in 2020 and 2021, the ratio of public debt to GDP rose by a whopping 119% in 2021. (Ramakumar, Op.cit.: 15)
- **Foreign Exchange Crisis**– The root cause of Sri Lanka's economic crisis was running persistent and large fiscal deficits, which were increasingly financed by unsustainable public debt, particularly foreign commercial borrowings. (Samarakoon: 2024) The Sri Lankan debacle set in with sudden import restrictions. As the Island nation imports most of its fuel requirements and other essential goods and commodities from abroad. It failed to do so owing to dwindling foreign exchange reserves. Therefore, the government was helpless in importing ample quantities in time and keeping them ready for distribution. The shortage of two items, i.e. LPG and diesel, was at the heart of the Sri Lankan economic fiasco and power outage for the most part of the day. (Radhakrishnan, 2022: 4) This spiralled into a crisis where power cuts and scarcity of fuel resulted in malfunctioning in every sector.
- **Tax Reduction and Money Creation** – The government of Sri Lanka under President Gotabaya Rajapaksa made large tax cuts that affected

government revenue and fiscal policies, causing budget deficits to soar. (Bala, 2022) Not only were taxes slashed, but VAT, as a significant source of revenue generation, was also slashed from 15 per cent to 8 per cent. To make matters worse, the Nation Building Tax, the PAYE tax and economic service charges were abolished. Indirect taxes, standard and corporate income tax rates were slashed from 28 per cent to 24 per cent. The personal income tax waiver was raised from LKR 500,000 to LKR 3000,000. (Ramakumar, Op.cit.:15) To patch up government spending, the Central Bank began printing money in record amounts, ignoring International Monetary Fund (IMF) advice to stop printing money and instead hike interest rates and raise taxes while cutting spending. (IMF Report)

- **Agricultural Crisis**—Sri Lanka's decision to go for extensive organic farming and ban inorganic fertilizer greatly affected the dismantling of the economy. The passing of the anti-fertilizer act by the parliament (later reversed, but ironically, chemical fertilizer was no longer subsidized) led to a drastic reduction in crop yielding in the agriculture sector and dependence upon foreign nations for rice, in which it was previously self-sufficient. (Nordhaus, 2022)

India's Humanitarian Support to Bail Out Sri Lankan Economic Crisis

The Indian Premier, Sri Narendra Modi, and the Sri Lankan President, Mr Ranil Wickremesinghe, unanimously acknowledged that the India-Sri Lanka partnership has been a pillar of strength in overcoming the island nation's economic crisis. Mr Ranil Wickremesinghe hailed India's unprecedented and timely support to the government and the people of Sri Lanka. (Ministry of External Affairs, 2023)

During the COVID-19 pandemic, India supplied more than 25 tons of medicines on a special aircraft to Sri Lanka in May 2020. In addition, India has gifted 5,00,000 doses of Covid vaccine, "Covishield", to Sri Lanka in January 2021. In August 2021, India assisted in transporting liquid medical oxygen (140 MT), which Sri Lanka commercially procured. The Indian Naval Ship Gharial was deployed for expeditious delivery of humanitarian supplies of medicine and kerosene to Sri Lanka. Indian Air Force airlifted nano nitrogen fertilizers to meet Sri Lanka's urgent requirement in November 2021. India gifted 1 lakh Rapid Antigen Test kits to Sri Lanka in February 2022.(Patel, 2023)

India extended lines of credit to the tune of USD 4 billion for food, fuel, fertilizer and medicines. According to the Indian High Commission report, “India has given USD 5 billion to Sri Lanka as development assistance with more than USD 600 million as grants”. (Balachandran, 2022)

In July 2020, India entered into a \$400-million currency swap agreement with Sri Lanka, which provided much-needed liquidity to the Sri Lankan central bank to manage its balance of payments and stabilize its currency by ensuring the availability of foreign exchange to meet external obligations. By May 15 2022, India provided 400,000 metric tons of fuel to Sri Lanka through a USD 500 million credit line. India sent 80,000 metric tons of diesel and petrol to Sri Lanka a week later. According to Indian media, New Delhi has helped Sri Lanka defer repayment of loans totalling USD 1 billion under the Asian Clearing Union. Tamil Nadu, a southern state of India, decided to send 500 metric tons of milk powder, 40,000 metric tons of rice and medicines to Sri Lanka. India has further assured to supply 65,000 metric tons of urea. (Kuruwita, 2022) Under the Neighbourhood First policy and the Security and Growth for All the Region (SAGAR) project, India also sent daily necessities to Sri Lanka. (Raina, 2022: 13)

Besides being Sri Lanka’s largest trading partner, India is one of the prominent contributors to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). According to the Sri Lankan Central Bank, the sum total FDI from India so far exceeds US\$ 2.2 billion. India’s FDI amounted to US\$ 142 million in 2021. The prominent investment areas from India are tourism & hotels, petroleum retail, telecommunications, manufacturing, real estate, and banking & financial services. (High Commission of India, 2023)

Trade and investment apart, India has remained the largest market for tourists visiting the Emerald Island. Post-COVID-19, tourism-related travel has witnessed an unprecedented surge owing to the conclusion of the Air Bubble Agreement between the two nations in April 2021. Of the 1,94,495 tourist arrivals to Sri Lanka in 2021, 56,268 were from India alone, about 29%. The numbers of international tourists visiting Sri Lanka stands at 719,978, of which 123,004 tourists (17.1%) were from India, making it the most significant contributor to tourism in Sri Lanka in 2022. (Ibid.)

Both nations entered into an air travel bubble arrangement to restore air connectivity in April 2021, impacted by the pandemic-related travel restrictions. In

October 2021, the Kushinagar Airport was inaugurated by the Indian Premier, Narendra Modi. It is hoped to generate substantial revenue for Sri Lanka as it is predominantly a Buddhist nation. “In 2020, Sri Lanka received USD 15 million as grant assistance from India for protecting and promoting Buddhist ties between India and Sri Lanka”. (Ibid.)

India also provided the Sri Lankan forces with a Dornier Aircraft, a naval floating dock for the Sri Lankan navy, apart from setting up the Maritime Resume coordination centre in Colombo. Maritime connectivity is very much in the rader for Indo-Sri Lankan cooperation and prosperity, and India is fully committed to developing ports and logistics infrastructure at Colombo, Trincomalee and Kankesanthurai that will up the ante for Lankan economic revival and prosperity. Both nations have taken a step in the right direction by resuming passenger ferry services between India’s Nagapattinam and Kankesanthurai in Sri Lanka and from Rameshwaram in India to Talaimannar in Sri Lanka to resume soon. (Ministry of External Affairs, Op.cit.)

Energy and Power connectivity will be significant and go a long way, paving the way for prosperity. The signing up of the MoU on collective cooperation in setting up renewable energy would propel Sri Lanka’s significant renewable energy potential, including offshore wind and solar power, thereby enabling Sri Lanka to achieve its objective of fulfilling nearly 70% of the power required from renewable energy sources by 2030. (Ibid.) India is more than eager to establish a high-capacity power grid interconnection between India and Sri Lanka to enhance bidirectional electricity trade with Sri Lanka by drastically reducing the electricity costs in Sri Lanka and creating a valuable and reliable source of foreign exchange for Sri Lanka. In this way, reliable and affordable Indian power can help Sri Lanka overcome electricity shortages and develop its own wind energy trade potential. (Wignaraja, 2023)

In 2022, as the fuel shortage in Sri Lanka due to low foreign exchange reserves can be mitigated by sending Indian oil that can be paid in Indian rupees, it may lower exchange costs and facilitate trade credits. India has also undertaken the erection of a multi-purpose petroleum pipeline from the Southern part of India to Sri Lanka for an affordable and sustainable source of energy to the Sri Lankan shore. (Ibid.)

India has also collaborated to develop Sri Lanka’s upstream petroleum sector and to produce hydrocarbons

in Sri Lanka's offshore basins. India has also expedited the implementation of the solar power project in Sampur and LNG infrastructure and collaborations in the production of green ammonia and hydrogen through innovative technologies to enhance the renewable energy mix to generate power in Sri Lanka. (Ministry of External Affairs, Op. cit.)

India has also vigorously pursued the development of tank farms and beneficial cooperation projects in the Trincomalee area, transforming it into a regional and national hub of industry, energy, and economic activities on a mutually understanding basis.

India has decided to designate INR as the currency for trade settlements between the two nations to forge robust and mutually beneficial commercial linkages. It has also agreed to operationalize UPI-based digital payments to further trade and transactions between businesses and common people.

As People-to-people Connectivity plays a prominent role in the progress and prosperity of the nation, India has endeavoured to create public awareness to popularize India's Buddhist circuit and Ramayana trail and vigorously promote ancient places of Buddhist, Hindu and other religious tourism spots for enhancing tourism.

As education is the lifeblood of progress and prosperity, India is extending cooperation between educational institutions from both sides and heftily funding to establish new higher education and skill development campuses in Sri Lanka. India is also extending unstinting, wholehearted collaboration and support to promote research and setting up of academic institutes in areas of mutual interests like IT, agriculture, aquaculture, business, finance and management, earth and marine sciences, health and medicine, space applications, oceanography, as well as culture, history, literature, languages, religious studies and other humanities.

CONCLUSION

India has also initiated land connectivity between both nations, specifically developing land access to the ports of Trincomalee and Colombo, to fuel economic growth and prosperity for all and further consolidate its age-old relationship. There were so many factors like power struggles, political mismanagement, pandemic outbreaks and economic challenges snowballing into crises of unparalleled magnitude since her independence in 1948. In the hour of her gravest crisis, India, like a trustworthy

neighbour, showed genuine concern to pull the precarious economy through a slew of initiatives leading to the strengthening up of bilateral ties and exploration of many promising but uncharted territory for growth and prosperity with the promise of a better dawn for both the neighbouring nations of South Asia.

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